

On Fixed Points in B-Rectangular Metric Spaces

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 15 May 2025</p> <p>Corresponding Author: A.S. Saluja</p>	<p>This paper presents fixed point results in b-rectangular metric spaces. The results obtained expand and generalize several well-established findings in the existing literature.</p> <p>2020 Mathematics Subject Classification: Primary: 54H25; Secondary: 54E50, 47H10.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Fixed point, b-metric space, rectangular metric space, b-rectangular metric space.</p>	

1. INTRODUCTION

In 1922, Banach proved his classical contraction principle. The investigation of existence and uniqueness of fixed point for a self mapping and common fixed point for two or more mappings has become a very active and natural subject of interest. Many researchers proved Banach contraction principle in multitude of generalized metric space.

In particular, b-metric spaces were introduced by Bakhtin [2] and Czerwik [6] as a generalization of metric spaces. They proved Banach contraction principle in b-metric spaces.

2. PRELIMINARIES

Definition 2.1 ([2],[6]) let X be a non empty set and $s \geq 1$ be a given real number. A function $d: X \times X \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is a b-metric on X if, for all $x, y, z \in X$ the following conditions hold:

- (b1) $d(x, y) = 0$ iff $x = y$
- (b2) $d(x, y) = d(y, x)$
- (b3) $d(x, z) \leq S[d(x, y) + d(y, z)]$ (b-triangular inequality)

In this case the pair (X, d) is called a b-metric space

Definition 2.2 [1] let X be a non empty set, and let $d: X \times X \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ be a mapping such that for all $x, y \in X$ and all distinct points $u, v \in X$, each distinct from x and y :

- (r1) $d(x, y) = 0$ iff $x = y$
- (r2) $d(x, y) = d(y, x)$
- (r3) $d(x, y) \leq d(x, u) + d(u, v) + d(v, y)$ (rectangular inequality)

Then (X, d) is called rectangular or generalized metric space or Branciari's space.

Definition 2.3 [4] let X be a non empty set, $s \geq 1$ be a given real number and let

$d: X \times X \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ be a mapping such that for all $x, y \in X$ and distinct $u, v \in X$, each distinct from x and y :

- (br1) $d(x, y) = 0$ iff $x = y$
- (br2) $d(x, y) = d(y, x)$
- (br3) $d(x, y) \leq S[d(x, u) + d(u, v) + d(v, y)]$ (b-rectangular inequality)

Then (X, d) is called a b-rectangular metric space or a b-generalized metric space (bg.m.s)

Note: that every metric space is a b-rectangular metric space and every rectangular metric space is a b-rectangular metric space (with coefficient $s=1$) However the converse is not necessarily true.

Also, every metric space is a b-metric space and every b-metric space is a b-rectangular metric space (not necessarily with the same coefficient)

3. MAIN RESULT

Theorem 3.1 : let (X, d) be a complete b-rectangular metric space with $t > 2$ and let $h, k: X \rightarrow X$ be two self maps satisfying,

$$d(hx, ky) \leq \delta P(x, y) + QR(x, y) \tag{3.1.1}$$

For all $x, y \in X$ where $\delta \in [0, \frac{1}{t}]$ and $Q > 1$ and

$$P(x, y) = \max\{d(x, y), d(x, hx), d(y, ky)\},$$

$$R(x, y) = \min\{d(x, hx), d(y, ky), d(x, ky), d(y, hx)\}.$$

Then h and k have a unique common fixed point.

Proof: let α_0 be an arbitrary point in X .

Define the sequence $\{\alpha_n\}$ in X as $\alpha_{2n+1} = h\alpha_{2n}$ and $\alpha_{2n+2} = k\alpha_{2n+1}$ for $n \geq 1$

Suppose that there is some $n \geq 1$ such that $\alpha_n = \alpha_{n+1}$

If $n = 2m$ then $\alpha_{2m} = \alpha_{2m+1}$ and from (3.1.1)

$$d(\alpha_{2m+1}, \alpha_{2m+2}) = d(h\alpha_{2m}, k\alpha_{2m+1})$$

$$\leq \delta P(\alpha_{2m}, \alpha_{2m+1}) + QR(\alpha_{2m}, \alpha_{2m+1})$$

Where $P(\alpha_{2m}, \alpha_{2m+1}) = \max\{d(\alpha_{2m}, \alpha_{2m+1}), d(\alpha_{2m}, h\alpha_{2m}), d(\alpha_{2m+1}, k\alpha_{2m+1})\}$

$$P(\alpha_{2m}, \alpha_{2m+1}) = \max\{d(\alpha_{2m}, \alpha_{2m+1}), d(\alpha_{2m}, \alpha_{2m+1}), d(\alpha_{2m+1}, \alpha_{2m+2})\}$$

$$P(\alpha_{2m}, \alpha_{2m+1}) = \max\{0, 0, d(\alpha_{2m+1}, \alpha_{2m+2})\}$$

$$R(\alpha_{2m}, \alpha_{2m+1}) = \min\{d(\alpha_{2m}, h\alpha_{2m}), d(\alpha_{2m}, \alpha_{2m+1}), d(\alpha_{2m}, k\alpha_{2m+1}), d(\alpha_{2m+1}, h\alpha_{2m})\}$$

$$= \min\{d(\alpha_{2m}, \alpha_{2m+1}), d(\alpha_{2m+1}, \alpha_{2m+2}), d(\alpha_{2m+1}, \alpha_{2m+1})\} = 0$$

Thus we have,

$$d(\alpha_{2m+1}, \alpha_{2m+2}) \leq \delta d(\alpha_{2m+1}, \alpha_{2m+2})$$

Which is a contradiction with $\delta \in [0, \frac{1}{t}]$

Therefore $\alpha_{2m+1} = \alpha_{2m+2}$ Thus we have $\alpha_{2m} = \alpha_{2m+1} = \alpha_{2m+2}$

It means that $\alpha_{2m} = h\alpha_{2m} = k\alpha_{2m}$

That is α_{2m} is a common fixed point of f and g

If $n = 2m + 1$ then using same arguments, it can be shown

that α_{2m+1} is a common fixed point h and k

Now suppose that $\alpha_n \neq \alpha_{n+1}$ for all $n \geq 1$

$$d(\alpha_{2n+1}, \alpha_{2n+2}) = d(h\alpha_{2n}, k\alpha_{2n+1}) \leq \delta P(\alpha_{2n}, \alpha_{2n+1}) + QR(\alpha_{2n}, \alpha_{2n+1})$$

...(3.1.2)

Where

$$P(\alpha_{2n}, \alpha_{2n+1}) = \max\{d(\alpha_{2n}, \alpha_{2n+1}), d(\alpha_{2n}, h\alpha_{2n}), d(\alpha_{2m+1}, k\alpha_{2n+1})\}$$

$$= \max\{d(\alpha_{2n}, \alpha_{2n+1}),$$

$$d(\alpha_{2n}, \alpha_{2n+1}), d(\alpha_{2n+1}, \alpha_{2n+2})\}$$

$$= \max\{d(\alpha_{2n}, \alpha_{2n+1}),$$

$$d(\alpha_{2n+1}, \alpha_{2n+2})\}$$

And

$$R(\alpha_{2n}, \alpha_{2n+1}) = \min\{d(\alpha_{2n}, h\alpha_{2n}), d(\alpha_{2n+1}, k\alpha_{2n+1}), d(\alpha_{2n}, k\alpha_{2n+1}), d(\alpha_{2n+1}, h\alpha_{2n})\}$$

$$= \min\{d(\alpha_{2n}, \alpha_{2n+1}), d(\alpha_{2n+1}, \alpha_{2n+2}),$$

$$d(\alpha_{2n}, \alpha_{2n+2}), 0\}$$

$$= 0$$

If $P(\alpha_{2n}, \alpha_{2n+1}) = d(\alpha_{2n+1}, \alpha_{2n+1})$ then by (3.1.2)

$$d(\alpha_{2n+1}, \alpha_{2n+2}) \leq \delta d(\alpha_{2n+1}, \alpha_{2n+2})$$

Which is a contradiction.

Thus $P(\alpha_{2n}, \alpha_{2n+1}) = d(\alpha_{2n}, \alpha_{2n+1})$

And from (3.1.2)

$$d(\alpha_{2n+1}, \alpha_{2n+2}) \leq \delta d(\alpha_{2n}, \alpha_{2n+1})$$

Similarly it can be proved that

$$d(\alpha_{2n+3}, \alpha_{2n+2}) \leq \delta d(\alpha_{2n+2}, \alpha_{2n+1})$$

So,

$$d(\alpha_{n+1}, \alpha_n) \leq \delta d(\alpha_n, \alpha_{n-1}) \leq \delta^n d(\alpha_1, \alpha_0) \text{ for all } n \geq 1.$$

Similarly we can show

$$d(\alpha_{n+2}, \alpha_n) \leq \delta^n d(\alpha_2, \alpha_0)$$

We can show that $\{\alpha_n\}$ is a b-rectangular - Cauchy sequence.

using b-rectangular inequality and

$\alpha_n \neq \alpha_{n+1}$ for all $n \geq 1$ and $d_n = d(\alpha_n, \alpha_{n+1})$,

$$d_n^* = d(\alpha_n, \alpha_{n+2})$$

$$d(\alpha_n, \alpha_{n+2m+1}) \leq t[d(\alpha_n, \alpha_{n+1}) + d(\alpha_{n+1}, \alpha_{n+2}) + d(\alpha_{n+2}, \alpha_{n+2m+1})]$$

$$\leq t[d_n + d_{n+1}] + t^2[d_{n+2} + d_{n+3}] + t^3[d_{n+4} + d_{n+5}] + \dots + t^{m+1}d_{n+2m}$$

$$\leq t[\delta n d_0 + \delta_{n+1} d_0] + t^2[\delta_{n+2} d_0 + \delta_{n+3} d_0] + \dots + t^m \delta_{n+2m} d_0$$

$$= \frac{1+\delta}{1-t\delta^2} t \delta^n d_0 \quad (t\delta^2 < 1)$$

$$\text{Hence, } d(\alpha_n, \alpha_{n+2m+1}) \leq \frac{1+\delta}{1-t\delta^2} t \delta^n d_0$$

...(3.1.3)

Similarly we can show that

$$d(\alpha_n, \alpha_{n+2m}) \leq \frac{1+\delta}{1-t\delta^2} t \delta^n d_0 + \delta^{n-2} d^*_0 \quad \dots(3.1.4)$$

Thus from (3.1.3) and (3.1.4) we obtain that

$$\lim d(\alpha_n, \alpha_{n+p}) = 0 \text{ for all } p = 1, 2, 3$$

... $n \rightarrow \infty$

Hence $\{\alpha_n\}$ is a b-rectangular -cauchy sequence in (X, d) .

By completeness of (X, d) , $\exists r \in X$ such that $\alpha_n = h\alpha_{n-1} \rightarrow r$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$

Now we prove that $hr = r$ (by b-rectangular-inequality)

$$\frac{1}{t} d(hr, r) \leq d(hr, k\alpha_n) + d(k\alpha_n, \alpha_n) + d(\alpha_n, r) \leq \delta P(r, \alpha_n) + QR(r, \alpha_n) + d(\alpha_{n+1},$$

$$\alpha_n) + d(\alpha_n, r)$$

Where $P(r, \alpha_n) = \max\{d(r, \alpha_n), d(r, hr), d(\alpha_n, k\alpha_n)\} \rightarrow d(r, hr)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$

$R(r, \alpha_n) = \min\{d(r, hr), d(\alpha_n, k\alpha_n), d(r, g\alpha_n), d(\alpha_n, hr)\} \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$

Hence taking the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain

$$\frac{1}{t} d(hr, r) \leq \delta d(r, hr) + Q \cdot 0 + 0 + 0$$

That is $hr = r$.

Hence r is a fixed point of h .

Now we show that $kr = r$. Suppose that $r \neq kr$ by (3.1)

$$d(r, kr) = d(hr, kr) \leq \delta P(r, r) + QR(r, r)$$

Where $P(r, r) = \max\{d(r, r), d(r, hr), d(r, kr)\} = \max\{0, 0, d(r, kr)\} = d(r, kr)$

$$\text{and } R(r, r) = \min\{d(r, hr), d(r, kr), d(r, kr), d(r, hr)\} = 0$$

By (3.1.1)

$$d(r, kr) \leq \delta d(r, kr)$$

Which is a contradiction.

Thus $kr = r$.

Now we show that uniqueness

Suppose r and s are different common fixed points of h and k

$$d(r, s) = d(hr, ks) \leq \delta P(r, s) + QR(r, s)$$

$$\text{where } P(r, s) = \max\{d(r, s), d(r, hr), d(s,$$

$$ks)\} = d(r, s)$$

$$\text{and } R(r, s) = \min\{d(r, hr), d(s, ks), d(r, ks), d(s, hr)\} = 0$$

Thus from (3.5)

$$d(r, s) \leq \delta d(r, s)$$

So $d(r, s) = 0$

i. e. $r = s$

4. CONCLUSION

As the rectangular b-metric space is relatively new addition two the existing literature. Therefore we endeavour to further enrich this notion by introducing the idea of extended rectangular b- metric spaces.

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